

Estimation of β -lactamase activity from multidrug resistant uropathological bacteria

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ABSTRACT

The urinary tract infection (UTI) is a bacterial infection of the urinary system in both community and healthcare settings. β -lactam antibiotics are the typical treatment option for UTI. But the increased rates of antibiotic resistance in bacteria have posed challenges in selecting the antibacterial agent. One of the mechanism bacteria developed to surpass the effect of β - lactam antibiotics is the production and secretion of β -lactamases (EC 3.5.2.6). These antibiotics have a common element in their molecular structure, a four-atom ring known as the β -lactam ring. The β -lactamases breaks this ring open, deactivating the molecule's antibacterial property. We have isolated and characterized the bacteria from UTI patients. The isolated bacteria were investigated for the antibiotic susceptibility towards commonly prescribed UTI antibiotics along with β -lactam antibiotics and isolated the multidrug resistant (MDR) clinical isolates. The secretary β -lactamase activities have been checked against eleven β -lactam antibiotics as a substrate by iodometric assay. This method depends upon the reduction of iodine by the hydrolyzed substrate.

Keyword: β -lactamase, iodometric method, urinary tract infection, multi drug resistance

INTRODUCTION

The urinary tract infection (UTI) is the infection of urinary tract that includes bladder infection (Cystitis) and/or kidney infection (Pyelonephritis). It is the second most common bacterial infection in humans after respiratory tract infection. UTI infection is more common in women compared to men [1] (Hooton 2011). Approximately 75-95% of UTIs are caused by *E.coli* but other common pathogens include *Proteus mirabilis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Enterobacter*, *Staphylococcus*, etc [2].

There is indisputable evidence that antimicrobial agents become progressively less effective with continued clinical use due to the evolution of resistant strains [3]. The principal mechanisms by which resistance to β -lactam antibiotics is achieved are changes in cell permeability [4-8] and enhanced production of β -lactamases [4,6-9]. Hence it is important to assay the β -lactamase activity in emerged MDR bacterial strains. Initially the enzymes were classified as being either chromosomally or R-plasmid mediated or of indeterminate genetic origin [10-14]. R-plasmid-mediated and potentially R-plasmid-mediated β -lactamases were considered to be more important epidemiologically, due to the ability of plasmids to rapidly transfer the structural genes for antibiotic resistance [15, 16]. The chromosomally mediated β -lactamases are species and subspecies specific [11].

The bacteria were isolated from patients with urinary tract infections. The multidrug resistance patterns were identified

for commonly prescribed antibiotics for UTI along with thirteen β -lactam antibiotics. The β -lactamase activity was estimated in MDR bacteria against selected β -lactam antibiotics by iodometric method [17].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Isolation and Identification of bacteria from uropathological samples: The urine samples (100) of UTI patients were collected in a sterile container from pathology laboratories and hospitals. The samples were diluted in 1:100 ratio with autoclaved distilled water and streaked on the LB-Agar plate. The plate was kept at 37^oC in an incubator for overnight. The bacterial colonies were isolated and identified. The characterization and identification of bacteria has been done by various tests [18].

Antibacterial sensitivity assay:

The isolated bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were tested for the susceptibility to antibiotics by disc diffusion method (Kirby-Bauer method) [19]. The antibiotics were purchased from Himedia, Mumbai. These are Ampicillin (A:5 μ g), Amoxicillin (Am:30 μ g), Chloramphenicol (C:30 μ g), Ciprofloxacin (Cf:5 μ g), Co-trimoxazole (Co:25 μ g), Cephalexin (Cp:30 μ g), Gatifloxacin (Gf:5 μ g), Kanamycin (K:30 μ g), Norfloxacin (Nx:10 μ g), Ofloxacin (Of:5 μ g), Penicillin-G (P:10 μ g), Pefloxacin (Pf:5 μ g), Streptomycin (S:10 μ g), Sparfloxacin (Sc:5 μ g), Tetracycline (T:30 μ g), Cefpodoxime

(CPD : 16 µg), Cephalexin (CN: 0.96 µg), Cefuroxime (CXM: 16 µg), Cefixime (CFM: 4 µg), Ceftazidime (CAZ: 2 µg), Cefazolin (CZ: 4 µg), Cefotaxime (CTX: 32 µg), Ceftriaxome (CTR: 0.48 µg), Cefaclor (CF: 32 µg), Feropenem (FAR: 8 µg), Cefepime (CPM: 32 µg).

Iodometric assay of β-lactamase

The estimation of the activity of β-lactamase can be done by Iodometric method. The method is described by Sawai et.al (1978) [17] which is a modification of Sargent [20] and Perret's iodometric method [21]. The basic principle of this method is that after adding β-lactam antibiotic as substrate into β-lactamase enzyme source, the β-lactamase hydrolyses the substrate, and this hydrolyzed substrate reduces the iodine. The amount of β-lactamase was estimated colorimetrically by measuring absorbance at 540nm. This method measures the iodine which is proportional to the amount of β-lactamase enzyme [17].

Preparation of crude extracellular β-lactamase extracts

30ml of autoclaved LB agar was mixed with ampicillin 100µg/mL as an inducer for beta-lactamase secretion. The isolated MDR isolates were streaked and the plate was incubated at 37°C for 18 hrs. 20 colonies of each isolate were taken from fresh LB plate cultures and mixed with 2 ml of 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.0). This was vortexed and used as an extracellular beta lactamase enzyme source.

Iodometry assay of beta lactamase

The standard procedure for assay of hydrolyzed β-lactam antibiotic was formed in which, β - lactamase in 2 ml of 0.1 M PBS buffer (pH 7.0) was pre incubated at 30°C for 5 min in an assay tube to which 1mg of the substrate solution was added with rapid mixing. A portion (300 µL) of the reaction mixture was removed at different intervals, and the reaction was stopped by addition of buffer and 5 ml of the iodine reagent. The final volume of the mixed solution was 8 ml. After the solution stood for 10 min at room temperature, its optical density was measured at 540 nm. Hydrolysis of the substrate led to a decrease in absorbance. After the substrate was completely hydrolyzed, the absorbance became

constant. All reagents were prepared as described by Sawai et.al [17].

The amount of substrate hydrolyzed in the assay tube was calculated from the following formula:

$$\text{Hydrolyzed substrate} = \frac{\Delta Ku}{Ku-\text{blank A}} \times \frac{40}{F}$$

The activity of β- lactamase enzyme was tested by using following formula.

$$\beta\text{- Lactamase activity (units per milliliter)} = \frac{\Delta Ku}{Ku-\text{blank A}} \times \frac{40}{F} \times \frac{1}{T} \times \frac{1}{V}$$

In these equations, ΔKu = (Ku-blank B) minus (Ku-sample). Ku-blank A, Ku-blank B, and Ku-sample, absorbance is expressed as Klett units; F, consumed of iodine (I2) per mole of the hydrolyzed substrate; T, time (minutes) for enzyme reaction; V, volume (milliliters) of enzyme solution added to the assay. One unit of enzyme activity was defined as that quantity which hydrolyzes 1 µmol of substrate per min.

β-lactam antibiotics used for assay

Cefpodoxime (CPD), Cephalexin (CN), Ampicillin (A), Cefixime (CFM), Ceftazidime (CAZ), Cefazolin (CZ), Cefotaxime (CTX), Ceftriaxome (CTR), Cefaclor (CF), Feropenem (FAR), Cefepime (CPM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isolation of bacteria

The percentage of bacteria isolated from UTI patients are *Escherichia coli* (26.37%), *Enterococcus faecalis* (35.16%), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (36.26%) and *Klebsiellapneumoniae* (2.19%) [18].

Study of Multidrug Resistant patterns

The isolated bacteria were checked for multidrug resistance (MDR). Following isolates were used for the β-lactamase assay.

Table-1: Selected MDR clinical isolates for beta lactamase assay

Bacteria	Clinical isolates	MDR pattern
<i>E. coli</i>	1 EC	A, Am, C, Cf, Co, Cp, Gf, K, Nx, Of, P, Pf, S, Sc, T, CPD, CN, CXM, CFM, CAZ, CZ, CTX, CTR, CF, CPM, FAR
	3 EC	A, Am, Cp, P, CPD, CN, CXM, CFM, CAZ, CZ, CTX, CTR, CF, FAR
	19 EC	S, CPD, CN, CXM, CFM, CAZ, CZ, CTR, CF, FAR
<i>E. faecalis</i>	1 EF	A, Am, C, Cf, Co, Cp, Gf, K, Nx, Of, P, Pf, S, Sc, T, CN, CFM, CZ, CTX, CTR, CPM, FAR
	4 EF	A, Am, C, Cf, Co, Cp, Gf, K, Nx, Of, P, Pf, S, Sc, T, CPD, CN, CXM, CAZ, CZ, CTX, CTR, CPM, FAR
	25 EF	A, K, Pf, CPD, CN, CXM, CFM, CAZ, CZ, CTX, CTR
	5 PA	A, Am, C, Cf, Co, Cp, Gf, K, Nx, Of, P, Pf, S, Sc, T, CPD, CN, CXM, CFM, CAZ, CZ, CTX, CTR, CPM, FAR

<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	14 PA	P, CPD, CN, CXM, CFM, CAZ, CZ, CTX, CTR, CPM,FAR
	32 PA	A, Am, Cp, P, CFM, CPM,FAR

Enzymatic hydrolysis of β -lactam antibiotics

All β -lactam antibiotics have been found to be hydrolyzed by β -lactamases. The hydrolysis of the different substrates led to the decrease in absorbance. It was found that after the substrate was completely hydrolyzed, the absorbance became constant (Fig-1, 2 and 3).

To confirm the complete hydrolysis of β -lactam antibiotic, the remaining solution of hydrolyzed substrate was used immediately for antibacterial activity by diffusion method [17]. For this assay the control ATCC strains of *E.coli*, *E. faecalis* and *P. aeruginosa* that are sensitive towards used β -lactam antibiotics have been used. No antibacterial activity was detected, indicating the hydrolysis of β -lactam antibiotics by β -lactamases. This also indicated the possible reason for emergence of drug resistance towards β -lactam antibiotics.

Fig-1: Hydrolysis of different β -lactam antibiotics by MDR clinical isolates of *E. coli*

Fig-2: Hydrolysis of different β -lactam antibiotics by MDR clinical isolates of *E. faecalis*

Fig-3: Hydrolysis of different β -lactam antibiotics by MDR clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa*

Table-2: Iodine consumption of the hydrolyzed β -lactam antibiotics

Substrates (β -lactam antibiotics)	Mean of F values			β -lactamase activity		
	EC	EF	PA	EC	EF	PA
Cefpodoxime	2.593	4.373	2.616	1.609	1.661	1.368
Cephalixin	3.897	4.312	2.554	0.355	0.447	0.625
Ampicillin	2.945	4.516	3.204	0.352	0.403	0.278
Cefixime	3.107	3.346	3.287	0.369	0.639	0.189
Ceftazidime	3.220	3.343	3.485	0.287	0.224	0.133
Cefazolin	3.351	4.356	2.635	0.278	0.769	4.071
Cefotaxime	4.033	4.242	4.775	0.216	1.062	0.531
Ceftriaxome	3.671	4.216	4.291	0.333	0.343	0.265
Cefaclor	2.962	6.716	3.539	1.444	0.474	1.487

Cefepime	2.547	4.273	2.825	1.711	0.357	1.508
Feropenem	3.312	3.759	3.269	0.326	1.937	0.343

EC- *E.coli*; EF- *E. faecalis*, PA- *P.aeruginosa*

Determination of β -lactamase activity

The activity of β -lactamase was calculated by the above mentioned formula [17]. F value which is defined as the number of iodine (I_2) molecules consumed by the hydrolyzed substrate under appropriate conditions was determined experimentally for each β -lactam antibiotics. The following table-2 described the respective F-values and activity of β -lactamase for each substrate.

DISCUSSION

β -lactamase is an important enzyme that hydrolyses the β -lactam antibiotics and provides drug resistance to the bacteria. Iodometry is a simple, fast and cost effective method to assay the β -lactamase activity in bacteria. The enzyme was detected in all selected uropathogenic isolates and results indicate presence of multiple antibiotic resistance. From the substrate hydrolysis curves utilized in this study which are commonly prescribed by physician, it was observed that most of the β -lactam antibiotics were hydrolyzed by β -lactamase in approximately forty minutes. This study is useful in prescribing antibiotics to UTI patients.

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